

The Information Consumer Consumed by Information

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ABSTRACT

Infertility is a physically and mentally taxing medical condition that impacts one in every eight couples. This qualitative study employed semi-structured interviews to explore how individuals with infertility seek, use, and share information. As self-described knowledgeable experts, study participants identified seeking the information to counteract difficult emotional responses and obtain a sense of control. Thematic analysis of the findings revealed that individuals with infertility often feel consumed by the need to search for information constantly. This work seeks to expand discussions about how individuals engage with information and how high levels of emotional and physical investment in a topic may lead to the experience of feeling consumed by information.

KEYWORDS

health information; information behavior; information consumer; information engagement; information process

INTRODUCTION

Infertility is "a disease characterized by the failure to establish a clinical pregnancy after 12 months of regular, unprotected sexual intercourse or due to an impairment of a person's capacity to reproduce" (Vander Borht & Wyns, 2018, p. 2). Fertility treatments are demanding of patients, as they are required to self-administer injections and other medications and follow a strict timetable. Studies have explored in-person and online searching behaviors for infertility-related information (Slauson-Blevins et al., 2013). Individuals with infertility usually face negative social consequences, such as neglect, stigmatization, and social isolation (Gerrits, 1997; Hollos, 2003). Even in developed countries, limited social support and the high costs of treatments often not covered in standard health insurance coverage compound the distress individuals with infertility face (Schlesselman-Tarango, 2019), leading to increased feelings of shame and isolation (Leon, 2010). Previous information behavior research has sought to characterize information consumers and their information engagement – from active traditional information users and passive traditional information users (Huntington et al., 2002) to monitors and blunders (Miller, 1995), explored the influence of emotion and cognition on information seeking and use (Chen, 2022), and demonstrated the impacts of information marginalization, or pushing a particular population to the margin where their needs have been ignored or overlooked through technology, information, and data (Gibson & Martin, 2019). This study explored how individuals with infertility seek, use, and share information, with a focus on the systemic barriers these information consumers face in accessing information and emotional support.

METHODS

This study employed a qualitative interview approach to explore the challenges faced by individuals with infertility in obtaining and using relevant health information. One researcher was a longtime and active participant in a Kansas City-based infertility support group on Facebook that served as the recruitment pool. Two announcements were posted to the group requesting volunteers. Semi-structured interviews lasting 30 minutes to an hour were conducted in English via Zoom with the nine females who volunteered to participate in July and August of 2022. Participants were not incentivized to participate and were assigned a number to protect confidentiality. The researchers used open coding in Atlas.ti to develop a codebook for thematic analysis. The codes were then applied to the remaining interviews to explore the experiences of individuals with infertility as they find, use, and share health information.

FINDINGS

Interview discussions included a range of topics, from the infertility journey to preferred information sources to emotional responses. Themes related to feeling consumed by information are presented in this paper. Participants described themselves as knowledgeable experts due to their long-term investment in information on this topic and identified information as a balm for difficult emotional responses. When describing what led them to stop seeking, they often pointed to when they felt consumed by information.

Knowledgeable experts

Individuals experiencing infertility undertake significant research, developing a wealth of knowledge on this specialized topic. When asked how knowledgeable they feel about infertility, most participants responded that they felt quite knowledgeable. Participant 1 summarized her domain expertise: "Someone asked me if I was hosting a TED talk about what it would be about, and I said the reproductive system." This expertise is developed out of necessity; with a host of treatment-related acronyms and a laundry list of prescribed medications, patients are often required to become experts in administering their medications and following complicated directions carefully. For many, the process of personal experience with the topic led to becoming knowledgeable experts and helped them find meaning in a difficult process.

Information as a balm for emotional responses

The emotional responses to being diagnosed with infertility range from denial to shock, overwhelmed to frustration, and dumbfounded. The emotional toll that infertility takes can be one of the more difficult aspects: “It’s not the physical pain, and it’s not even the news necessarily [that] other things worked or not. It’s a pain of having to wait constantly” (Participant 3). Searching for information was a balm for the range of emotions experienced: “For me, the way that my anxiety processes things. I’m a researcher, and the more information I have, the calmer I feel, or the more prepared” (Participant 8). Participant 6 described information seeking specifically as a “coping mechanism. [I] was like, oh I’m really anxious about this, and I can’t sleep, so I’ll just read more articles.”

Stopping information seeking

When asked when they would stop looking for information, the reasons cited could be categorized based on their positive or negative experiences or feelings. Finding successful cases or satisfactory answers is one reason to stop seeking. However, information-seeking also often stops due to adverse situations, such as information overload. Participant 7 pointed out, “if I find myself ... looking at one article and [that] leads to another question ... I’ll try to break out of it.” Further, stopping occurs when information overload leads to feeling emotionally overwhelmed. Participant 10 explained, “sometimes I feel like I would go seeking reassurance online through Google ... at some points, the information becomes overloaded. It doesn’t make you feel any better. At that point ... It was just hurting me. I would have to turn it off.”

Consumed by information

After spending day after day waiting for a baby and looking for any scrap of information that might help them on their journey, individuals experiencing infertility find themselves consumed by finding and using infertility-related information. This novel expression of the act of information consumption consuming the information seeker derived directly from the participants in this study. As Participant 3 shared about infertility, “It consumes your life. Thinking about it and researching it all the time. Every day you’re thinking about what the next thing is and what you need to do.” This concept of feeling consumed was expressed in relation to being asked when they decided to stop looking for information and was a theme that emerged directly from the participants’ experiences. Different from the concept of information overload, or the inability to understand or make decisions due to too much information, being consumed by information emphasizes the negative impact on mental health and quality of life caused by the insatiable demand and constant search for information.

DISCUSSION

The participants in this study mirror patients with a monitoring coping style, as they “attend to threatening information” (Miller, 1995, p. 168). This study takes the monitoring versus blunting distinction one step further by identifying the phenomenon of being consumed by information. Beyond actively using information or monitoring, in cases where the need for and use of information is so high, the person may begin to feel consumed by the information process. This category of individuals who become consumed by finding and using information may be defined as the information consumed. The reason for stopping searching for health information is unique and can be attributed to information overload and the resulting emotional stress. Wang (2022) notes that such information overload can be due to an excessive reading of irrelevant information due to insufficient health information provided by medical professionals, emphasizing the importance of improving access to broad and in-depth infertility information resources.

CONCLUSION

This work seeks to continue the conversation about how individuals engage with information and how high levels of emotional and physical investment in a topic may lead to the experience of being consumed by information, extending the findings of Chen’s (2022) study and confirming the negative impact caused by uncertainty and lacking needed information. The idea of feeling consumed by the information process is a phenomenon that emerged from qualitative analysis of this study’s interview findings, but one that resonated with the authors and presents opportunities for future research in contexts where individuals become highly engaged on a singular topic (e.g., cancer, doctoral dissertation, serious hobbies, etc.). Each of the participants described motherhood as a core personal goal, and their long-term investment in the topic demonstrates a sustained, all-consuming process of finding and using infertility information.

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REFERENCES

- Chen, A. T. (2022). Interactions between affect, cognition, and information behavior in the context of fibromyalgia. *Journal of the Association for Information Science and Technology*, 73(1), 31-44.
- Gerrits, T. (1997). Social and cultural aspects of infertility in Mozambique. *Patient Education and Counseling*, 31(1), 39-48.

- Gibson, A. N., & Martin III, J. D. (2019). Re-situating information poverty: Information marginalization and parents of individuals with disabilities. *Journal of the Association for Information Science and Technology*, 70(5), 476-487.
- Hollos, M. (2003). Profiles of infertility in southern Nigeria: Women's voices from Amakiri. *African Journal of Reproductive Health*, 46-56.
- Huntington, P., Nicholas, D., Williams, P. & Gunter, B. (2002). Characterising the health information consumer: An examination of digital television users. *Libri: International Journal of Libraries & Information Services*, 52(1), 16-27.
- Leon, I. G. (2010). Understanding and treating infertility: Psychoanalytic considerations. *Journal of the American Academy of Psychoanalysis and Dynamic Psychiatry*, 38(1), 47-75.
- Miller, S. M. (1995). Monitoring versus blunting styles of coping with cancer influence the information patients want and need about their disease. Implications for cancer screening and management. *Cancer*, 76(2), 167-177.
- Schlesselman-Tarango, G. (2019). Reproductive failure and information work: An autoethnography. *Library Trends*, 67(3), 436-454.
- Slauson-Blevins, K. S., McQuillan, J., & Greil, A. L. (2013). Online and in-person health-seeking for infertility. *Social Science & Medicine*, 99, 110-115.
- Vander Borcht, M., & Wyns, C. (2018). Fertility and infertility: Definition and epidemiology. *Clinical Biochemistry*, 62, 2-10.
- Wang, T. (2022). *Rare disease, rare information: Investigating healthcare information use in online global disability support groups* (Publication No. 29259580). [Doctoral dissertation, Emporia State University]. ProQuest Dissertation Publishing.